

Designing a Roadmap for Effective and Sustainable Strategies for Assessing and Addressing the Challenges of EU Agriculture to Navigate within a Safe and Just Operating Space

A Joint Evaluation of Agri- Environmental Schemes and Organic Farming in the EU

Discussion paper

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A Joint Evaluation of Agri-Environmental Schemes and Organic Farming in the EU

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Abstract

Within Pillar II of the European Union’s Common Agricultural Policy, agri-environmental schemes (AES) — delivered under the Rural Development Regulation through the agri-environment-climate measure (Measure 10) and the organic-farming measure (Measure 11) — absorb a substantial share of public expenditure. These are two instances of the same class of policy, yet the applied literatures on Measure 10 and Measure 11 have evolved almost independently. This paper provides the first joint EU-wide causal evaluation of both on a common Farm Accountancy Data Network panel (2014–2020) under a single estimator that combines the double/debiased machine learning approach to difference-in-differences with staggered adoption (DML-SDiD). Identification draws on never-treated controls for Measure 10 and on not-yet-treated controls for Measure 11, reflecting the overlap properties of each measure’s candidate control pool. Disaggregated event-study estimates reveal that Measure 10 produces a windfall pattern for participating farms across four of five farm-type groups, with binding effects concentrated in specialist dairy. Measure 11 produces stable trajectories for livestock converters but a richer transitional pattern for mixed and crop converters, including sharp in-conversion reductions in synthetic input expenditure and a delayed post-certification income response.

Keywords: Common Agricultural Policy; agri-environmental schemes; organic farming; causal inference; staggered difference-in-differences; machine learning.

I INTRODUCTION

The European Union’s Common Agricultural Policy (CAP) dedicates a large and growing share of its budget to *green* instruments — policy tools that pay farmers for practices delivering environmental outcomes beyond the regulatory baseline. Within Pillar II of the CAP, the dominant green instruments are the so-called agri-environmental schemes (AES), implemented under the Rural Development Regulation (RDR) as voluntary, co-financed multi-year contracts (Hasler et al., 2022; Coderoni et al., 2024). Over the 2014–2020 programming period, AES were primarily delivered through two RDR measures: the agri-environment-climate measure (Measure 10), covering a menu of practices from reduced tillage and buffer strips to extensification and animal-welfare upgrades, and the organic-farming measure (Measure 11), which supports both conversion to and maintenance of certified organic production (European Commission, 2013; Coderoni et al., 2024). For this reason, throughout the paper, we use the term “AES” for the policy class that comprises both measures, while we refer to “Measure 10” (or “non-organic AES”) for the agri-environment-climate measure specifically, and “Measure 11” (or “organic-farming support”) for the organic measure specifically. Measure 11, singled out by the Farm-to-Fork strategy’s 25% organic-area target for 2030 (Meemken and Qaim, 2018; Finger et al., 2024), is therefore an AES in the full sense: a voluntary Pillar II contract, tied to a specified practice, and compensated on the standard income-foregone-plus-additional-costs logic. Thus, unlike much of the CAP evaluation literature, this manuscript does not implicitly treat organic support as something categorically distinct from other AES.

Using the European Farm Accountancy Data Network (FADN) for 2014–2020 and a single estimator that integrates the double/debiased machine learning difference-in-differences approach (Chang, 2020; Chernozhukov et al., 2018) with staggered adoption (Callaway and Sant’Anna, 2021), we estimate the dynamic effects of (i) participation in Measure 10 across five farm-type specializations and (ii) Measure 11 conversion for livestock and mixed/crop operations. As the two analyses draw on the same dataset and share the same estimators, they only differ in how treatments are defined, in which control pool identifies the counterfactual, and in the sample restrictions that make that counterfactual credible. A core benefit of placing the two applications side by side is that the comparison becomes one between sub-populations and contract designs within a unified AES framework, rather than a comparison whose results can be misleadingly attributed to different estimands, identifying assumptions and econometric approaches.

Despite the scale of public expenditure involved, the empirical basis on which these two measures rest remains contested. On the Measure 10 side, the evaluation literature largely acknowledges that the corresponding commitments lead to, for most farms, practices that farmers would have entertained even without the subsidized intervention. This has spurred a growing concern that the voluntary-menu, action-based design of the instrument systematically admits what is referred to as “windfall” effect¹. On the Measure 11 side, the evidence is context-dependent in a different way: organic certification is tightly regulated and its agronomic and economic consequences depend on the structural distance between pre-conversion practice and the organic standard, on the maturity of the premium market, and on the crop–climate combination in question. Both literatures share two recurring gaps that this paper seeks to address: EU-wide

¹i.e., payments flow to farms who would have adopted the practice anyway.

dynamic estimates are scarce, and the two measures are seldom evaluated on the same panel and under the same estimator, so that comparisons across them are contaminated by differences in method rather than reflecting differences in the policies themselves.

Closing these gaps is non-trivial because AES evaluation carries three well-known methodological hurdles simultaneously: farms self-select into participation on a complex bundle of observable and unobservable characteristics that are hard to absorb with standard parametric controls; enrollment is staggered across years and cohorts, which is known to bias two-way fixed-effects and canonical difference-in-differences estimators (Callaway and Sant’Anna, 2021); and treatment is not a binary decision but unfolds over a multi-year horizon during which adjustments evolve — particularly for organic conversion, which is itself a regulated multi-year process (European Commission, 2025). Addressing high-dimensional non-linear selection, staggered timing, and multi-year dynamics jointly is what has kept the literature from producing EU-wide dynamic evidence. This paper therefore leverages the comprehensiveness of the EU-wide FADN to implement an estimator designed to handle all three simultaneously. In particular, we build upon the staggered-DiD approach of Callaway and Sant’Anna (2021) to recover group–time average treatment effects on the treated (ATTs) under a conditional parallel-trends assumption tailored to cohort-specific timing. We next extend it to incorporate the doubly/debiased Machine Learning (DML) component introduced by Chang (2020) that replaces parametric specifications of the relevant nuisance functions — the propensity score and the outcome regression — with flexible machine-learning (ML) estimators that absorb complex, non-linear selection without imposing functional-form restrictions. The feasibility of combining these two approaches has recently been suggested in the causal inference literature: Sant’Anna and Zhao (2020) derive the doubly-robust DiD estimand that the staggered framework of Callaway and Sant’Anna (2021) aggregates, while Chernozhukov et al. (2018) and Ahrens et al. (2025) show that ML-based nuisance estimation with Neyman-orthogonal moments and cross-fitting is valid for any DR estimand of this form. To our knowledge, however, this is the first empirical study that explicitly combines the two methods into a single staggered estimator with ML-estimated nuisances.

While we adopt the same econometric approach for estimating the causal effect of adopting Measure 10 and Measure 11, the two applications do differ in one substantive methodological aspect. The latter is extremely important for reliably quantifying the policy impact of the CAP AES. Specifically, the identification of group–time treatment effects requires (among other important assumptions) overlap: for any profile of pre-treatment characteristics X at which treated farms are observed, comparable untreated farms must also be observed. Which untreated farms make overlap plausible depends on the policy. For Measure 10, the literature suggests non-participating farms are widely distributed across the covariate space, making it relatively easy to find untreated farms that resemble treated farms at plausible baseline X ; the never-treated (NT) pool is therefore a credible counterfactual. For Measure 11, on the other hand, farms that remain conventional throughout the window are typically known to be structurally different from farms that eventually convert, and at plausible baseline X it is hard to find comparable matches among the permanently conventional population. Therefore, overlap is restored by conditioning on the not-yet-treated (NYT) pool. In other words, farms that will convert later on in time (but have not yet done so at the reference date) share a similar latent propensity to switch with

current organic farms and therefore sit much closer to the “treatment group” in covariate space. Therefore, the NT–NYT distinction is ultimately an overlap argument that follows directly from how each measure maps into the underlying data.

To sum up, this paper provides what is, to our knowledge, the first joint EU-wide causal evaluation of Measure 10 and Measure 11 on a common panel and under a common estimator, framed explicitly as two instances of the same policy class. Second, it proposes a new integration between staggered DiD and DML estimation that has not been documented in the literature yet. Third, and relatedly, we report dynamic event-time effects disaggregated by farm-type specialization for both measures — five FADN type-of-farming (TF) groups for Measure 10, and two aggregated groups (livestock, mixed/crop) for Measure 11 — producing a side-by-side reading that exposes sub-population-specific patterns that single-instrument studies typically miss.

The remainder of this paper is organized as follows. Section II provides the policy background on CAP Pillar II AES and positions Measure 10 and Measure 11 as two instances of a single policy class. Section III sets out the proposed estimator, the aggregation schemes used, and the identifying assumptions for each application. Section IV describes the FADN panel, outcome definitions, and the sample construction for each application, including a side-by-side summary table. Section V presents the event-study estimates: the Measure 10 results across the five TF groups (Section V.1) and the Measure 11 results for livestock and mixed/crop operations (Section V.2). Section VI offers a cross-case reading and derives the policy implications. Section VII concludes.

II BACKGROUND

The CAP is organized around two main pillars. While Pillar I provides direct payments and market-related support to farmers, Pillar II, delivered under the Rural Development Regulation (RDR) and financed through the European Agricultural Fund for Rural Development (EAFRD), funds a menu of rural development measures at the Member-State (or, in many countries, regional) level through multi-annual rural development programs. AES — introduced in the 1992 MacSharry reform and expanded in every subsequent reform — are the leading set of instruments through which Pillar II pursues environmental objectives, and they operate as voluntary, co-financed contracts that compensate farmers for the income foregone and the additional costs incurred when they adopt practices beyond the regulatory baseline of Pillar I (eco-)conditionality (Hasler et al., 2022). Over the 2014–2020 programming period, AES were mainly delivered through two RDR measures: the agri-environment-climate measure (Measure 10), covering a broad menu of practices ranging from extensification and buffer-strip creation to reduced pesticide use and animal-welfare upgrades, and the organic-farming measure (Measure 11), which supports both conversion to and maintenance of certified organic production. Measure 11 is therefore an AES in the standard sense — a Pillar II voluntary contract, tied to a specified practice, compensated on the standard logic — but it is a stricter variant, in ways developed below.

Within the AES family, Measure 10 and Measure 11 differ in three structural respects that matter for evaluation. First, Measure 10 covers a heterogeneous menu negotiated at Member-State level, whereas Measure 11 is anchored in a single, EU-wide regulatory definition of organic

production and is verified through third-party certification (Seufert et al., 2017). The scope of the commitment is therefore unambiguous under Measure 11 in a way that Measure 10 contracts, by design, often are not. Second, the organic-conversion process is itself tightly regulated: farmers must adopt organic practices for a mandated period before they are legally allowed to market output as organic.² This conversion phase creates a clearly identified in-conversion state that is distinct from both the pre-treatment conventional state and the post-certification state. Such a conversion period is not as clearly defined in Measure 10, where some of the sub-measures may specifically recognize the need for a subsidized transition, while others may not. Third, the bundle of practices covered by organic certification — prohibition of synthetic fertilizers and pesticides, restrictions on livestock density, traceability requirements — is, in general, broader and more prescriptive than most Measure 10 contracts. Therefore, for the purposes of causal evaluation, Measure 11 reads as a more prescriptive and strictly regulated (with the involvement of third-party certifications) variant of other AES: better-defined treatment, better-identified conversion window, and a more demanding practice bundle.

Despite their scale and the hefty budget allocation, the empirical basis for AES policy design remains contested, and the two bodies of evidence that have developed around Measure 10 and Measure 11 have largely developed independently.

In this respect, the evaluation literature on Measure 10 and its pre-2014 analogues converges on a fairly consistent narrative characterized by a relatively small and uncertain impact of these commitments on farm economic outcomes. These tiny or null effects are typically found in sub-populations where the contracted practice binds against the core production technology of the farm, i.e. the farms where Measure 10 is expected to bring about a structural change do not coincide with those that voluntarily adhere to the policy instrument (Pufahl and Weiss, 2009; Chabé-Ferret and Subervie, 2013; Arata and Sckokai, 2016; Mennig and Sauer, 2019; Bertoni et al., 2020; Uehleke et al., 2022). The same pattern shows up when the outcomes are environmental rather than economic: only a minority of treated farms record a change of the sign and magnitude that the contract targets, and a non-negligible share moves in the opposite direction (Batáry et al., 2015; Jones et al., 2017; Stetter et al., 2022; Coderoni, Esposti, and Varacca, 2024). The way that these results are most commonly interpreted is that the action-based, voluntary-menu architecture of Measure 10 exposes the instrument to three compounding problems: adverse self-selection, in which farms already compliant with the contracted practice in the absence of the policy enroll disproportionately; inadequate administrative targeting, in which voluntary measures attract participation that is spatially and structurally decoupled from environmental need; and ill-enforced conditionality, in which payments reward actions rather than verified outcomes (Armsworth et al., 2012; Kuhfuss et al., 2016; Wunder et al., 2020). The resulting concerns of windfall effects are thus pervasive enough that a growing part of this literature explicitly asks whether Measure 10 contracts, as designed, can deliver additionality at a level that is detectable net of sampling variation (DuPraz and Latruffe, 2015; Hasler et al., 2022). Although

²Under Regulation (EU) 2018/848, conversion periods are two years for annual crops, three years for perennial crops, twelve months for bovine and equine animals raised for meat, six months for dairy cattle, and shorter periods for small ruminants and poultry. For operational reasons, and because FADN does not distinguish sub-categories within our livestock farm type (TF) groups at the required granularity, we aggregate conversion windows to one year for livestock (TF45, TF49) and two years for mixed/crop operations (TF15, TF16, TF80) throughout the empirical analysis.

the evidence seems to align across several empirical studies, most of these are country-specific (Germany, France, Italy, Bavaria in particular), rely on identification strategies tailored to a single programming context, and global EU-wide estimates are either scarce or miss the dynamic nature of these interventions (Zimmermann and Britz, 2016).

The evaluation literature on Measure 11 has developed along a somewhat different track, which is most likely attributable to several concurrent factors. First, the regulatory content of organic certification is comparatively well defined: EU organic regulation constrains synthetic fertilizer and pesticide use, livestock density, and crop rotation through explicit and third-party-verified rules rather than through a menu of voluntary options, and these constraints apply uniformly across the converting population (Seufert, Ramankutty, and Mayerhofer, 2017). Second, the agronomic consequences of these constraints are context-dependent. Meta-analytic evidence documents a mean organic-versus-conventional yield gap of around 18 per cent, with substantial variation by crop type, climate, and soil (de la Cruz et al., 2023), and this gap coexists with typically favourable effects on biodiversity, soil health, and input-efficiency indicators (Reganold and Wachter, 2016; Meemken et al., 2021), although evidence diverges depending on whether the outcomes are measured per unit of land or unit of output. Third, the economic viability of organic production depends on premium-market access at least as much as on yields: global evidence points to a profitability premium for organic relative to conventional operations that is driven by output prices rather than by closing the yield gap (Crowder and Reganold, 2015), and systematic reviews of the adoption literature conclude that the policy measures most strongly associated with scaling organic agriculture are supply-chain and market measures rather than adoption subsidies alone (Möhring, Muller, and Schaub, 2024). Fourth, the farms that convert are not a random subset of conventional farms. That is, early adopters systematically differ from the average conventional farmer on structural characteristics such as pre-existing extensification, pasture-based feeding, and management orientation, while later adopters face different frictions and different institutional support (Padel, 2001). For the economic-evaluation problem specifically, the implication is that converting populations are heavily self-selected on precisely the characteristics that drive post-conversion performance, and that the relevant counterfactual for a given converter is not a randomly drawn conventional farm. As with Measure 10, however, EU-wide dynamic estimates are scarce: most work treats certification as a static switch rather than a multi-year conversion process with distinct economic phases (Seufert and Ramankutty, 2017).

Conceptually, the same additionality-versus-windfall question applies to both measures, but the design regimes under which the question is asked are substantively different — voluntary-menu and action-based in one case, regulated and certified in the other — and so are the sub-populations that each measure reaches. For example, a grass-fed livestock operation that enters Measure 11 but was already operating extensively may exhibit minimal adjustment in observed outcomes, mirroring the windfall case on the Measure 10 side. A conventional cereal operation undertaking the two-year organic conversion may exhibit visible transitional costs in fertilizer and pesticide expenditure, and potentially in income, as synthetic inputs are withdrawn and rotations are rebuilt — the additionality case.

III METHODOLOGICAL FRAMEWORK

As previously mentioned, evaluating the causal effects of participation in either measure requires an estimation strategy capable of addressing four methodological challenges simultaneously. First, effects are dynamic: both Measure 10 and Measure 11 unfold over multi-year horizons during which economic and agronomic adjustments evolve (Pufahl and Weiss, 2009; Mennig and Sauer, 2019; Seufert and Ramankutty, 2017). Second, enrollment is staggered: farms enter treatment in different years, and, for Measure 11, the legally mandated conversion period — one year for livestock, two years for mixed and field-crop systems — is itself a distinct treatment phase that must be modeled separately from the fully certified phase. Third, treated and control farms differ systematically on unobserved characteristics such as soil quality, management ability, and market access (Möhring et al., 2024); these differences interact non-linearly with the treatment response in ways that standard parametric models struggle to accommodate (Storm et al., 2020). Last, the estimator should be constructed in such a way that the counterfactual group can be assembled using either NT or NYT individuals. The subsections that follow set out the econometric approach that, by design, covers all four of the above-mentioned aspects.

III.1 The staggered DiD estimator with a flexible control pool

Our primary statistical estimand of interest targets the group–time average treatment effect on the treated, $ATT(g, t)$, defined for each cohort of farms first entering treatment in year g and each post-treatment period $t \geq g$. The staggered-DiD architecture of Callaway and Sant’Anna (2021) represents one of several frameworks developed in response to the documented biases of two-way fixed-effects estimators under staggered adoption and (time-)heterogeneous treatment effects such as the ones characterizing our analysis (Goodman-Bacon, 2021; de Chaisemartin and D’Haultfœuille, 2020; Sun and Abraham, 2021; Borusyak et al., 2024). We choose to follow the approach by Callaway and Sant’Anna (2021) for two important reasons that matter for our applications: it explicitly accommodates conditioning on pre-treatment covariates, which is essential for the DML layer, and it admits a not-yet-treated comparison pool, which is what the Measure 11 application requires. The doubly-robust $ATT(g, t)$ estimator proposed by the authors takes the form

$$ATT^c(g, t) = \mathbb{E} \left[\left(\frac{G_g}{\pi_g} - \frac{\frac{p_{g,t}(X) C^c}{1-p_{g,t}(X)}}{\mathbb{E} \left[\frac{p_{g,t}(X) C^c}{1-p_{g,t}(X)} \right]} \right) [Y_t - Y_{g-1} - \ell_{g,t}^c(X)] \right] \quad (1)$$

where G_g is a binary indicator for farms first entering treatment in year g , $\pi_g = \mathbb{E}[G_g]$, D_t is the treatment status at t , Y_t and Y_{g-1} are the outcome of interest at t and at the reference period immediately before g , and X is the vector of pre-treatment farm characteristics. The superscript $c \in \{\text{nt}, \text{nyt}\}$ indexes the comparison pool: C^{nt} restricts the conditioning set to farms that are never treated over the window, while C^{nyt} restricts it to farms that have not yet been treated by period t . Specifically, $C_i^{\text{nt}} = 0$ if farm i has never applied for any AES ($C_i^{\text{nt}} = 1$ otherwise), while $C_i^{\text{nyt}} = (1 - D_t)(1 - G_g)$. Equation (1) generalizes the doubly-robust estimator of Sant’Anna and Zhao (2020) to staggered settings and — by indexing the comparison pool — accommodates both the non-organic AES application (with $c = \text{nt}$) and the organic-conversion application (with

$c = \text{nyt}$).

The two terms $p_{g,t}(X)$ and $\ell_{g,t}^c(X)$ in (1) are typically referred to as nuisance functions in the sense of Chernozhukov et al. (2018). These are the generalized propensity score, $p_{g,t}(X)$, i.e. the conditional probability of belonging to cohort g given covariates X , and the outcome regression, $\ell_{g,t}^c(X)$, i.e. the conditional expectation of the outcome change $Y_t - Y_{g-1}$ for the comparison pool. Neither is the object of direct interest, but both must be estimated consistently to quantify $ATT(g, t)$. The doubly-robust property of (1) ensures that the estimand remains consistent if either $p_{g,t}(X)$ or $\ell_{g,t}^c(X)$ is correctly specified — a weaker requirement than the joint correctness that is usually required by other popular estimators that rely on inverse probability weighting or regression adjustment.

III.2 Machine learning for the nuisance functions

Conventional estimators typically rely on low-dimensional parametric specifications for the two nuisance components. In the EU FADN setting, where farm heterogeneity is substantial and the relevant covariate set is large, such specifications are unlikely to capture the true functional relationships for either the generalized propensity score or the outcome regression components (Storm et al., 2020). The double/debiased ML framework introduced by Chernozhukov et al. (2018) and adapted to DiD settings by Chang (2020) addresses this limitation by allowing $p_{g,t}(X)$ and $\ell_{g,t}^c(X)$ to be estimated with flexible machine-learning algorithms that learn non-linear patterns directly from the data. In this respect, two well-known hazards of naively applying ML estimation in causal settings — regularization bias and overfitting — are handled by Neyman-orthogonal moment conditions and by K -fold cross-fitting, which together guarantee consistency and asymptotic normality of the causal estimator under standard regularity conditions. In this respect, Chang (2020) demonstrates how the score function discussed by Chernozhukov et al. (2018) can be easily mapped to the 2X2 DiD design, which guarantees Neyman orthogonality³ of the resulting cross-fitted estimator. Since the doubly robust ATT in equation (1) can be formulated as a straightforward group-time blocked generalization of the estimator discussed in Chang (2020), the good asymptotic properties of the latter carry over to the Callaway and Sant’Anna (2021) formulation of equation (1), when the nuisance parameters have been estimated using ML methods.

In our implementation, we estimate both nuisance functions via a stacked ensemble (“superlearner”) combining three regularized algorithms: random forests, gradient boosting, and penalized regression. Ensemble weights are assigned on the basis of predictive performance (area under the ROC curve for the propensity score, out-of-sample R^2 for the outcome regression). This ensemble approach reduces sensitivity to any single model’s misspecification and stabilizes estimates across cohorts (Ahrens et al., 2025). Covariates undergo a Yeo–Johnson transformation and standardization before entering the learners. Cross-fitting is carried out over four folds.

³Neyman orthogonality is a property of the estimating equation (or “score function”) that ensures the causal parameter of interest is locally insensitive to errors in the estimation of high-dimensional nuisance parameters

III.3 Identifying assumptions

Equation (1) identifies $ATT(g, t)$ under five assumptions, four of which are common across the two applications and one — the choice of comparison pool — which differs substantively.

Common assumptions. (i) *No anticipation*: farms do not alter outcomes before entering treatment in year g . For Measure 10 this is plausible because contract terms and payment streams begin at enrollment, so pre-enrollment behavioral changes would impose costs without compensation. For Measure 11, the formal in-conversion phase already entails costly adoption of organic practices without access to organic price premia, so advancing those practices further would only extend the period of reduced profitability. (ii) *Irreversibility*: once farms enter the treatment at time g , they remain treated for the whole period (i.e. until $\max(t)$). Although this assumption reads very restrictively, it is worth stressing that under both Measure 10 and 11, applying farmers are required a minimum time commitment that, depending on the type of farm or the specific sub-measure contracts, can last up to several years (generally between 5 and 7 years, although some exceptions typically apply). In practice, we also exclude the small fraction of treated farms that revert to untreated status (0.58% in the Measure 11 sample); the Measure 10 sample-filtering rule of continued participation through 2020 handles this by construction. (iii) *Conditional parallel trends*: conditional on X , untreated potential outcomes evolve in parallel for treated cohorts and the comparison pool (Abadie, 2005; Chang, 2020). The DML component of the estimator is devised to make this assumption weaker than in most DiD studies by allowing the conditioning set, X , to enter flexibly rather than through a researcher-specified parametric form. (iv) *Common support and SUTVA*: covariate distributions overlap between treated cohorts and the comparison pool, and treatment of one farm does not materially affect outcomes on others (Imbens and Rubin, 2015). Spatial spillovers are partially addressed by including the regional share of treated farms at baseline as a pre-treatment covariate, though this is a control rather than a full correction; landscape-scale spillovers from biodiversity- or water-quality-oriented contracts could, in principle, contaminate the counterfactual in either direction, and we do not take a strong stand on the residual sign. Section VI returns to this point among the limitations.

The comparison-pool assumption. As introduced in Section I, Assumption (vi) governs which untreated farms serve as the counterfactual and is one of the places where the two applications diverge. Once again, it is worth noting that the split between NT and NYT reference pools is an overlap argument. For Measure 10, the comparison pool is the set of *never-treated* farms (NT), i.e., farms that record no AES or animal-welfare subsidies across the entire 2014–2020 window. At plausible baseline X , this assumption states that it is relatively easy to find untreated farms that resemble treated farms: non-participating farms are broadly distributed across the covariate space, and positivity on $p_{g,t}(X) < 1$ holds across all five TF groups. This choice follows standard practice in the Measure 10 evaluation literature (Arata and Sckokai, 2016; Mennig and Sauer, 2019; Stetter et al., 2022). For Measure 11, the never-treated pool does not support overlap. For baseline covariate profiles at which conversion is plausible, farms that never convert are expected to be scarce or absent. The reason is that conversion is tied to persistent structural and managerial characteristics — management orientation, pre-existing extensification, regional

market access — on which permanently-conventional farms are structurally different from those that eventually switch to the organic technology. In this case, conditioning on X does not fix the problem: common support fails and positivity is violated, which makes causal identification unattainable. We therefore use the NYT pool: for farms converting in year t , the comparison pool is farms that convert in $t' > t$ but are still conventional at t . The staggered rollout thus supplies a dynamic control group whose members share the latent disposition to convert, so that at any baseline X treated farms have higher chances to find close matches. This is the standard solution for absorbing-state treatments with persistent selection (Callaway and Sant’Anna, 2021).

III.4 Inference and aggregation

Inference on the vector of $ATT(g, t)$ estimates is conducted via the multiplier bootstrap procedure of Callaway and Sant’Anna (2021), modified to account for the additional uncertainty from the ML-estimated nuisance functions. This procedure yields simultaneous confidence bands with nominal coverage across the full (g, t) grid, protecting against the multiple-testing problem inherent in event-study plots.

Moreover, since the group–time $ATT(g, t)$ estimates are numerous and not directly interpretable, we aggregate them into two complementary event-study parameters, each suited to a different part of the analysis. The first is the *calendar-time* average effect,

$$\theta^c(t) = \sum_{g \in \mathcal{G}} \mathbf{1}\{t \geq g\} ATT(g, t) \Pr(G = g \mid G \leq t),$$

which averages effects across all cohorts treated by period t . We use $\theta^c(t)$ for pooled results where cohort composition is relatively balanced across the time window. The second is the *balanced event-time* average of Callaway and Sant’Anna (2021),

$$\theta_{es}^{bal}(e; e') = \sum_{g \in \mathcal{G}} \mathbf{1}\{g + e \leq T\} ATT(g, g + e) \Pr(G = g \mid G + e' \leq T),$$

which averages effects by length of exposure e , restricting the sample to a constant set of cohorts for which the full exposure sequence is observable. This restriction prevents compositional change in the underlying cohort set from contaminating the dynamic pattern. For the Measure 10 application, $\theta_{es}^{bal}(e)$ is the primary object of interest: it delivers the event-study trajectory on which the windfall-versus-additionality reading rests. For the Measure 11 application, we also use $\theta_{es}^{bal}(e)$ within livestock and within mixed/crop sub-analyses, where it allows us to map estimated effects directly onto the regulated conversion windows and to separate the in-conversion phase from the fully-certified phase.

Each $\theta_{es}^{bal}(e)$ is defined relative to the reference period $e = -1$, i.e., the year immediately preceding entry into treatment. The bounded pre-treatment horizon ($e \in \{-2, -1\}$) is retained by design: extending it further back reduces the balanced sample to later-adopting cohorts only and lowers statistical power across the full trajectory.

IV DATA

IV.1 The FADN panel

Both applications draw on the European Farm Accountancy Data Network (FADN), the EU-wide rotating panel of commercial farms collected under a stratified sampling design across all EU-28 Member States (DG AGRI, 2023). The panel tracks 228,910 unique farms over 2004–2020, yielding 1,375,715 observations. FADN captures cultivation plans, economic and financial indicators, labor inputs, subsidies received, and a set of geographical and structural variables; it is the most comprehensive source of farm-level data in the EU, covering approximately 90% of EU agricultural land and production (DG AGRI, 2023).

The analysis window is 2014–2020, corresponding to the 2014–2020 CAP programming period. The decade 2004–2013 is used to compute pre-treatment covariate averages, and the two years immediately before the treatment window — 2012 and 2013 — serve as placebo pre-treatment periods for both applications. Restricting treatment to within the 2014–2020 window ensures that treated and control farms operate under the same CAP policy architecture, eliminating a source of confounding that would otherwise arise from cross-reform comparisons (Padel, 2001).⁴

IV.2 Treatment definitions

The two applications apply different treatment indicators to the same panel. In the case of Measure 10, following the EU-level AES evaluation literature, we define a farm as treated from the first year it records a positive amount of subsidies under the FADN “agri-environmental and animal welfare” category, after removing farms that also receive organic support under Measure 11 (Hasler et al., 2022; Coderoni et al., 2024). This binary indicator represents the most comprehensive measure of Measure 10 participation available at the EU level and abstracts from Member-State-specific scheme design, which varies substantially in payment levels and eligibility rules. For Measure 11, using the FADN organic-certification indicator (code `A_CL_140_C`), we define a farm as treated from the first year it enters the in-conversion status. This code distinguishes between conventional, in-conversion, partially organic, and fully organic statuses, and it offers two advantages over a subsidy-based definition. First, certification status is consistently defined across Member States, irrespective of national payment design. Second, it avoids the timing misalignments that occur when FADN data collection precedes subsidy administration, which would otherwise incorrectly record some participating farms as untreated.

In both cases, we make sure that neither “false treated” or “false controls” are included in the sample. First, we discard farms for which no pre-treatment information is available. Second, if, for any farm, we could not observe the year preceding the first treatment evidence, that farm is also excluded from the data. Third, in case of missing values between g and $\max(t)$, we assume missingness at random because of the rotating nature of the FADN panel. Moreover, in case of inconsistent treatment indicators for $t > g$ (for example, farms that, for a single year, switch back to conventional when they should have been organic for the whole window, given measure

⁴Because FADN is a rotating panel, farms are not observed every year. FADN’s stratified sampling design — by region, economic size, and farm-type — is driven by structural criteria rather than by farm-level treatment decisions, so panel rotation should not introduce systematic selection into the analysis.

11 commitments), we use the assumption of treatment irreversibility and impute the expected treatment status.

IV.3 Sample construction and comparison pools

Table 1 summarizes the sample construction for each application.

Table 1: Sample construction — Measure 10 (non-organic AES) vs Measure 11 (organic conversion).

Dimension	Measure 10 (non-organic AES)	Measure 11 (organic conversion)
Treatment indicator	First year of AES/animal-welfare subsidy (2014–2020)	First year of in-conversion status (FADN A_CL_140_C)
Comparison pool	Never-treated (NT)	Not-yet-treated (NYT)
Pre-2014 exclusions	Farms receiving AES subsidies before 2014; organic farms; farms already in-conversion at first observation	Farms already organic or in-conversion at first observation
Continuation requirement	Participation through 2020	Full conversion trajectory observed (conventional → in-conversion → fully organic)
TF disaggregation	TF15, TF16, TF45, TF49, TF80 (five groups)	Livestock (TF45, TF49 pooled); mixed/crop (TF15, TF16, TF80 pooled)
Treated N (total)	12,788	1,689
Treated N (by year)	See Table 2	See Table 3
Analysis window	2014–2020	2014–2020

The asymmetry in sample size reflects structural features of the two measures. Measure 10 covers a broad set of practices and admits a large NT pool after the pre-2014 filter, which is what allows the finer disaggregation by TF specialization reported in Section V. Measure 11, by contrast, is a narrower and more prescriptive AES whose clean identification requires stricter data restrictions. The remaining 1,689 treated farms are observed with precise timing and complete trajectory information, which is what supports the balanced event-time aggregation.

Table 2: Measure 10 (non-organic AES) — number of treated units by adoption year and FADN type of farming (TF).

	Cereals & protein (TF15)	Other fieldcrops (TF16)	Dairy (TF45)	Livestock (TF49)	Mixed (TF80)	Total
NT pool ($g=0$)	8,070	4,530	5,586	1,901	3,171	23,258
<i>Treated cohorts by adoption year (g)</i>						
2014 ($g=1$)	2,067	1,100	2,725	1,559	1,759	9,210
2015 ($g=2$)	287	278	682	379	189	1,815
2016 ($g=3$)	178	88	156	80	106	608
2017 ($g=4$)	107	85	122	62	48	424
2018 ($g=5$)	80	76	63	50	28	297
2019 ($g=6$)	53	50	72	45	29	249
2020 ($g=7$)	47	47	53	15	23	185
Treated total	2,819	1,724	3,873	2,190	2,182	12,788

Table 3: Measure 11 (organic conversion) — number of new treated units and not-yet-treated controls by cohort year g .

Cohort year (g)	New treated	Share (%)	Not-yet-treated controls
2014 ($g=1$)	313	18.5	1,376
2015 ($g=2$)	326	19.3	1,050
2016 ($g=3$)	299	17.7	751
2017 ($g=4$)	233	13.8	518
2018 ($g=5$)	176	10.4	342
2019 ($g=6$)	221	13.1	121
2020 ($g=7$)	121	7.16	0

Total: 1,689 unique farms; 10,773 observations. NYT units for the last period are zero by construction.

Three observations on sample composition are worth emphasizing for the results that follow. First, the Measure 10 sample is heavily concentrated in 2014: 9,210 of the 12,788 treated observations (72%) enter in that year, reflecting the timing of the CAP programming period. Event-study estimates at long exposure horizons therefore rest disproportionately on the 2014 cohort, a caveat that bears on confidence-band width at $e \geq 5$. Second, in the Measure 11 sample, treatment entry is more evenly distributed across 2014–2020, with no single cohort exceeding 20% of new entrants. Third, the NYT pool shrinks mechanically toward zero as the window closes, which is why the balanced aggregation (Section III.4) restricts the horizon to exposures for which a stable cohort set is available.

IV.4 Outcomes

Both applications examine farm-level performance along a common core of three outcomes: gross farm income per hectare (net of subsidies; FADN code SE410), total specific costs per hectare (SE281), and labor input measured in annual working units per hectare (SE010). All three are analyzed in logarithms to facilitate percentage interpretation and address heteroskedasticity.⁵ Gross income is reported net of organic-specific subsidies and AES payments, so that the estimated ATT captures adjustments in farm performance rather than the payments themselves.

For mixed/crop farm types — both the Measure 10 TF groups (TF15, TF16, TF80) and the Measure 11 mixed/crop group — we add three agronomically relevant outcomes: expenditure on fertilizers per hectare (SE295), expenditure on pesticides per hectare (SE300), and a land-use diversity index (Shannon index over cultivated crops, following Coderoni et al., 2024). Fertilizer and pesticide expenditures are adjusted by a Member-State- and year-specific price index (Eurostat, 2024); expenditure is used rather than physical quantity both because farm-level quantity data are not reported in the EU-28 FADN and because the heterogeneity of active ingredients would limit the interpretability of aggregated quantities even if they were (Möhring et al., 2019). Clearly, these additional outcomes are not included in the livestock sub-analyses, as they are not structurally informative for specialist livestock operations (TF45, TF49 in the Measure 10 application; the livestock sub-sample in the Measure 11 application), where feed

⁵The three core outcomes (income, costs, labor) are reported in log points, which admit a percentage interpretation. Fertilizer and pesticide expenditure (introduced below) are instead reported in levels, as €/ha, because log-transforming expenditure variables with a non-trivial mass of zeros — common during the organic in-conversion phase, when synthetic fertilizers and pesticides are prohibited — induces a censoring that distorts the event-study reading. The Shannon land-use diversity index is reported on its native 0–2 scale.

and animal welfare are the binding practice changes that the two measures are supposed to encourage.

IV.5 Covariates

Following Hünermund et al. (2023), we do not feed the ML learners an indiscriminate set of FADN variables, but select covariates based on the available literature on AES and organic adoption. The covariate set includes 46 pre-treatment variables spanning structural characteristics (farm size, legal form, labor organization), geographical and environmental factors (region, altitude, agronomic zone), production-system attributes (livestock density, cropping pattern, machinery intensity), input-use intensity (variable costs, energy expenditure), economic indicators (turnover, subsidies from other Pillar II measures), and a set of region-level controls capturing the density of participating farms at baseline. Pre-treatment averages are computed on the 2004–2013 sub-window; for categorical variables, the latest available value is used. The full covariate list is identical across the two applications for comparability; minor TF-specific adjustments — for instance, the exclusion of dairy-specific variables in crop-dominated TFs — are applied where the agronomic structure demands it.

V RESULTS

We report dynamic event-time estimates for both applications using the balanced aggregation $\theta_{es}^{bal}(e)$ introduced in Section III.4. Each point estimate is displayed with its simultaneous 95% confidence interval from the multiplier bootstrap. Pre-treatment estimates at $e \in \{-2, -1\}$ serve as placebo tests for the conditional parallel-trends assumption and should be statistically indistinguishable from zero. Income, costs, and labor outcomes are reported at the logarithmic level (percentage interpretation); fertilizer and pesticide expenditures are reported in €/ha at the Member-State- and year-harmonized price level; the land-use diversity index is reported on its native 0–2 scale.

The results for Measure 10 (Section V.1) are disaggregated into the five FADN type-of-farming (TF) groups introduced in Section IV. Within each TF cohort we report the core three outcomes — log income, log costs, and log labor — and, where agronomically meaningful, the three additional outcomes of fertilizer expenditure (€/ha), pesticide expenditure (€/ha), and the land-use diversity index. The results for the Measure 11 application (Section V.2) are disaggregated by conversion-window structure: livestock (one-year conversion) and mixed/crop (two-year conversion). Following the rationale set out in Section IV.4, livestock outcomes are restricted to income, costs, and labor; mixed/crop outcomes include the three agronomic outcomes as well.

V.1 Measure 10

The event-study estimates for the five TF groups deliver a coherent overall story that, with one notable exception, points to windfall rather than additionality. The exception is specialist dairy (TF45, Figure 1), where pre-treatment estimates are indistinguishable from zero but post-entry income drops by between 5% and 12% relative to the never-treated counterfactual and remains

significant across the full exposure horizon, while costs are broadly stable. Although there appears to be a violation of parallel trends assumption, the resulting profile is one of persistent income reduction (net of the subsidy) unaccompanied by offsetting cost adjustments, consistent with the AES evaluation literature that documents genuine behavioral adjustment — reduced stocking density, pasture-based feeding, nitrogen limits — in dairy systems (Mennig and Sauer, 2019). Specialist non-dairy livestock (TF49, Figure 2) displays a similar directional pattern at a smaller magnitude, with income effects typically in the 2–5% range and confidence intervals that include zero for most exposures, with a slight and persistent increase in costs and a labor effect that is statistically indistinguishable from zero.

Figure 1: Event-study estimates for specialist dairy farms (TF45) under Measure 10 (non-organic AES) enrollment.

Figure 2: Event-study estimates for specialist livestock farms (TF49) under Measure 10 (non-organic AES) enrollment.

Mixed crop-livestock farms (TF80, Figure 3) show effects that are economically small and statistically indistinguishable from zero on all six outcomes, with income, costs, and labor estimates close to zero throughout, fertilizer and pesticide estimates below $\pm\text{€}5/\text{ha}$, and a land-use diversity index that moves within ± 0.02 points on a 0–2 scale — a range that the agronomic literature treats as practically negligible. The stability of all six outcomes, including the two pre-treatment placebos, is consistent with a windfall reading: participating farms were already broadly aligned with the newly stipulated practice, and the policy produces income transfer

without observable behavioral adjustment (Wunder et al., 2020). The cereals-and-proteins group (TF15, Figure 4) differs from the other TFs in that income estimates remain close to zero with a modest positive drift in mid-term exposures that later drops below zero, labor increases by 2–5% post-adoption, costs rise by 5–7% over the horizon, and — most notably — fertilizer and pesticide expenditures *rise* post-enrollment, by up to €4.31/ha and €3.39/ha at $e = 3$, while the land-use diversity index stays flat. Taken together, this pattern seems consistent with mild intensification rather than extensification — the opposite sign of the adjustment that Measure 10 contracts typically target for field-crop operations — and with payments being used alongside intensification rather than as compensation for it. This interpretation would read as a sharper windfall effect than the economically small patterns observed for TF80. We return to this in Section VI. One important caveat with the results for TF15 is that four out of six outcomes do not seem to satisfy the parallel trend assumption, as evidenced by the significant treatment effect in the pre-treatment window. Thus, any implication drawn from these empirical findings should be treated with due caution. Other fieldcrop farms (TF16, Figure 5), a broad heterogeneous group covering specialist oilseeds, root crops, and horticulture, display the weakest overall response: income, costs, and fertilizer estimates are close to zero across the horizon with confidence intervals containing zero at every post-treatment exposure, labor exhibits a modest downward trajectory of roughly 2–5% that is directionally opposite to the TF15 pattern but of similar magnitude and statistical ambiguity, and pesticide expenditure and land-use diversity are flat. These results also support the windfall hypothesis.

Figure 3: Event-study estimates for mixed crop-livestock farms (TF80) under Measure 10 (non-organic AES) enrollment.

Figure 4: Event-study estimates for cereal and protein-crop farms (TF15) under Measure 10 (non-organic AES) enrollment.

Figure 5: Event-study estimates for other fieldcrop farms (TF16) under Measure 10 (non-organic AES) enrollment.

V.2 Measure 11

Measure 11 results are also reported using the balanced exposure-time aggregation $\theta_{es}^{bal}(e)$ with the exposure axis aligned to the regulated conversion window: one year for livestock (Figure 6) and two years for mixed/crop (Figure 7). This alignment allows estimated effects to be mapped directly onto the in-conversion phase and the fully-certified phase. The reference period is $e = -1$, i.e., the year immediately preceding entry into the conversion window.

The two sub-samples deliver markedly different pictures. For livestock (Figure 6), pre-treatment estimates at $e = -2$ and $e = -1$ are close to zero across all three outcomes, with reasonably consistent conditional parallel trends. During the brief conversion phase at $e = 0$, income, costs, and labor show no statistically significant changes and point estimates remain within a narrow band around zero. Upon achieving fully certified organic status from $e = 1$ onward, income point estimates follow a progressively upward trajectory with positive effects emerging at $e = 3$ and $e = 4$, though confidence intervals continue to contain zero for most exposures so that the pattern is more suggestive than conclusive. Costs and labor also remain remarkably stable throughout both phases. The overall reading of the results is consistent with livestock farms already operating extensively before conversion — stocking densities below regulatory binding constraints, pasture-based feeding regimes, and labor organizations compatible with organic certification requirements — for which certification is substantially procedural and any modest post-certification income gains reflect market premium access rather than structural change. This is the livestock counterpart of the windfall effect observed in the Measure 10 panel for TF80 and TF16.

Figure 6: Event-study estimates for livestock Measure 11 converters (one-year conversion window).

The mixed and crop sub-sample (Figure 7) tells a substantially richer story, and the pattern separates cleanly between the in-conversion phase and the fully-certified phase. Income is volatile during conversion ($e = 0, 1$), with confidence intervals containing zero throughout; at $e = 4$ — two years after completion of the two-year conversion, into the certified phase — income shows a positive and statistically significant spike of approximately 20%,⁶ becoming statistically insignificant at $e = 5$ where the smaller sample also widens the confidence interval, a trajectory consistent with income recovery once transitional costs have been absorbed and organic premia materialize. Overall production costs remain relatively stable throughout conversion and the early certified phase, with a modest statistically significant decline of approximately 11% emerging at

⁶Euro-per-hectare translations of log-point effects reported in this section are ex-post calculations computed at sample means; they are not estimated directly and do not appear on the figure axes.

$e = 5$. Labor point estimates are close to zero throughout the conversion and certified phases and confidence intervals contain zero at every post-treatment exposure, so the mixed/crop panel provides no statistically significant evidence of labor adjustment to conversion. Interestingly, fertilizer expenditure shows the sharpest adjustment, falling by roughly €87–107/ha during the conversion phase, consistent with the regulatory prohibition on synthetic fertilizers, and then recovering toward pre-treatment levels after full certification. Pesticide expenditure follows a similar pattern, with declines of roughly €47–105/ha during conversion followed by recovery in later exposures. Understanding both of these trends also requires considering the stability of the treatment effects for the cost outcome. This cost stickiness might indicate that farmers re-allocate budget towards capital restructuring and/or more expensive farming practices. On the other hand, the reverting trend at $e = 3$ might suggest that, once certification is obtained and the new subsidies and premiums become available, farms begin to purchase new and more expensive authorized inputs. The Shannon land-use diversity index, defined on a 0–2 scale, is stable through most of the horizon, with a single statistically significant decline of approximately 6% at $e = 5$ that is too small to represent a meaningful cropping-pattern shift.

Figure 7: Event-study estimates for mixed and crop Measure 11 converters (two-year conversion window).

VI DISCUSSION AND POLICY IMPLICATIONS

VI.1 Measure 10: non-organic AES

The prior evidence broadly suggests that Measure 10-type instruments produce average economic effects that are small and statistically weak on most participating farms, with binding behavioural change concentrated in a minority of sub-populations for which the contracted practice constrains core production technology, and with the balance of the response consistent with windfall rather than additionality. This is read in the literature as a joint consequence of voluntary-menu participation, action-based payment, and weak administrative targeting — each of which the

pre-2023 programming architecture largely did not correct.

Not only our estimates are consistent with this picture, but they also sharpen it in three respects. First, the windfall regime we find on four of five TF groups is not only a Member-State result nor a consequence of a particular identification strategy: it also appears when analyzing the EU-wide sample covered by the FADN, under a staggered estimator and across outcomes that include economic performance (income, costs, labor) and agronomic behaviour (fertilizer and pesticide expenditure, cropping diversity). Second, the TF group in which we do find a persistent effect — specialist dairy (TF45) — matches the kind of sub-population in which the prior literature locates binding adjustments: post-enrollment income falls by 5–12 per cent net of the subsidy while costs remain broadly stable, consistent with contracts that restrict stocking density and feeding regime. Third, the cereals and protein-crop group (TF15) carries a signal that is directionally inconsistent with the environmental intent of most Measure 10 contracts for field-crop operations: post-enrollment fertilizer and pesticide expenditures rise, not fall. Moreover, because the pre-treatment placebos for several TF15 outcomes do not clearly satisfy the parallel-trends assumption, we treat this signal as mostly association (rather than a causal effect), but we report it anyway because the direction is the opposite of what a well-targeted scheme should deliver.

The policy implication is that Measure 10 instruments would benefit from a redesign toward outcome-linked additionality: tighter eligibility screening to reduce enrollment of already-compliant farms, stronger per-TF targeting calibrated to where binding constraints actually exist, and conditioning of payments on verifiable changes in practice or outcome rather than on contractual adoption alone. In the post-2023 architecture⁷, the Pillar I eco-scheme layer — whose annual contracts can be revised more flexibly — could be a natural vehicle for screening, while the Pillar II agri-environment-climate commitments — whose multi-year horizons allow verification of behavioral change — should be a natural vehicle for outcome-linked contracts. In this context, however, it is worth stressing that the farmer-protest movements of 2023–2024 have already produced a partial retreat from some of these ambitions at the EU level (Finger et al., 2024), which complicates the political feasibility of tightening but does not change the efficiency case for it.

VI.2 Measure 11: organic-farming conversion

The prior evidence on organic farming broadly suggests that the economic response to conversion is context-dependent rather than uniform, and that the relevant context is the structural distance between pre-conversion practice and the organic standard, the maturity of the premium market, and the crop–climate combination in question. On that reading, any disaggregated evaluation of Measure 11 should expect a twofold response: sub-populations that already operate close

⁷The post-2023 CAP architecture has substantially redesigned the green layer of the policy: enhanced conditionality now merges the former greening payments with the baseline good-agricultural-and-environmental-condition standards that all Pillar I recipients must meet. Exceeding that baseline, Member States operate annual voluntary Pillar I eco-schemes whose menus partially overlap with those of the Measure 10 contracts analysed in this paper, while Pillar II retains the multi-year agri-environment-climate commitments derived from Measure 10 and the organic-farming commitments derived from Measure 11. Two open design questions in the new architecture are therefore the ones our estimates speak to: how to structure conditionality, eco-schemes, and Pillar II commitments so that payments deliver additionality rather than transfer, and how to calibrate organic support to the transition regime different sub-populations actually face.

to the organic standard — extensive livestock systems with stocking densities below binding regulatory constraints, pasture-based feeding regimes, labor organizations compatible with organic certification — should show small economic adjustment on conversion, since certification is substantively a procedural change that reprices output rather than re-engineering production. Sub-populations that sit further from the standard — mixed and crop systems facing synthetic-input prohibitions, rotation requirements, and non-trivial yield-gap exposure — should display more visible adjustment in input expenditure during the regulated conversion window and more visible income adjustment after certification, once premium-market access materializes.

Our estimates line up with this expected bifurcation. The livestock panel shows income, costs, and labor close to zero during conversion and into the certified phase, with income point estimates drifting modestly upward after certification but confidence intervals containing zero for most exposures. The mixed and crop panel, on the other hand, shows the sharpest adjustments in our analysis: fertilizer expenditure falls by roughly €87–107/ha and pesticide expenditure by roughly €47–105/ha during the conversion phase, with partial recovery toward pre-treatment levels as certified-organic input substitutes become available; a positive and statistically significant income effect emerges at $e = 4$, two years after the end of the two-year conversion window; and total costs remain broadly stable throughout, consistent with the absorption of higher-priced organic-compatible inputs alongside the withdrawal of synthetic ones. In this respect, the sign of the input response matches the regulatory content of the measure, while the timing of the income response matches the post-certification emergence of premium-market access that the wider literature identifies as the main economic margin of organic production. Moreover, the divergence between the livestock and mixed/crop panels matches the structural divergence between the two sub-populations.

Two policy implications are worth discussing. For livestock converters, for whom certification is largely procedural and the binding question is whether the post-certification premium materializes, the relevant policy layer is less the Pillar II conversion subsidy than the supply-chain, market-infrastructure, and information measures that are most strongly associated with scaling organic agriculture in the wider adoption literature (Möhring, Muller, and Schaub, 2024). For mixed and crop converters, for whom the conversion window imposes visible economic frictions on input withdrawal that precede any premium, the relevant policy layer is the support within Pillar II conversion commitments: financial support during the conversion window, extension and training services that lower the knowledge costs of conversion, and stable policy signals that reduce uncertainty over the conversion-to-certification trajectory. Calibrated support of this kind is already implemented unevenly across Member States (European Commission, 2023). Our evidence supports its harmonization and reinforcement as a key component of the Farm-to-Fork strategy, conditional on the political constraints that have recently reshaped the broader CAP reform trajectory.

VI.3 Limitations and future work

Our work has a few limitations worth acknowledging. First, the NT and NYT identification regimes are not strictly comparable, and while Section III formalizes the distinction, any cross-case reading remains a comparison of two credible-but-different counterfactuals rather than a

pooled estimate. Second, farm-level environmental outcomes — emissions, biodiversity, soil quality — are not observed in FADN at the granularity required for direct causal analysis; the input-substitution and land-use-diversity results reported here are proxies for, not measures of, environmental impact. Third, the fertilizer and pesticide expenditure measures conflate price and quantity effects, and do not distinguish between synthetic and organic-certified inputs at the level of detail that a full environmental accounting would require (Möhring et al., 2019).

The forthcoming transition of FADN to the Farm Sustainability Data Network (FSDN) is expected to lift several of these constraints from 2025 onwards (European Parliament and Council of the European Union, 2023), adding environmental and social indicators to the existing economic panel.

VII CONCLUSIONS

This paper provides a joint EU-wide causal evaluation of Measure 10 and Measure 11 — the two main agri-environmental instruments of CAP Pillar II during the 2014–2020 programming period — on a common FADN panel and under a common estimator that integrates the DML difference-in-differences approach with staggered adoption. The two applications share data source and estimator but differ in identification regime: never-treated controls for Measure 10, not-yet-treated controls for Measure 11. The split reflects the overlap properties of each measure’s candidate comparison pool rather than a design preference.

Our evidence largely aligns with previous findings in the existing literature. For Measure 10, prior research had converged on a reading in which action-based, voluntary-menu contracts generate small average treatment effects dominated by windfall, with binding behavioural change concentrated in sub-populations where the contract imposes constraints against core production technology. Our EU-wide event-study estimates are consistent with this understanding at all post-treatment horizons and across six outcomes, locating the one case of binding adjustment in specialist dairy, where post-enrollment income falls by 5–12% net of subsidies alongside broadly stable costs. For Measure 11, the prior literature suggests a context-dependent view in which economic viability hinges on premium-market access and the structural distance between pre-conversion practice and the organic standard. Our estimates are consistent with that reading as well: the sub-population closer to the organic standard at entry (livestock converters) displays stable outcomes through and after conversion, while the sub-population further from it (mixed and crop converters) shows sharp in-conversion reductions in fertilizer and pesticide expenditure, cost stability that is informative about input substitution rather than input reduction, and a delayed post-certification income response.

For policy design within the post-2023 CAP architecture, the evidence supports a differentiated calibration rather than a uniform recommendation. Measure 10 instruments — both the annual eco-schemes in Pillar I and the multi-year commitments in Pillar II — would benefit most from outcome-linked additionality screening and TF-level targeting, calibrated to the sub-populations where contracts bind. Measure 11 instruments would also benefit from differentiated conversion support distinguishing the sub-population undergoing genuine structural change and from supply-chain and market-infrastructure measures on the sub-population for which certification is largely procedural.

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